

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Rinchen**FIRST NAME:** Namgay**PROGRAM CODE:** DBIO**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 1**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 03%

The author used the software Microsoft 360 version 16 on Windows 11

List of Key Concepts:

1. Reflection on Course (ACA-401D)
2. The Essence of Good Essay (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024,9-11)
3. Punctuation
4. American Vs. British English
5. Style Guide and CMS (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 44-52)

REFLECTIONS ON ACADEMIC WRITING: INSIGHTS FROM THE ACA401D COURSE

1) INTRODUCTION

I have decided to pursue a Ph.D. in Bioethics through an online program at Euclid University. This choice aligns well with my present circumstances, allowing me to continue working while advancing my education. My background in medicine and public health, coupled with my interest in patients' rights and professional ethics in healthcare, makes this field particularly appealing to me. Moreover, as bioethics is a new field in my country, I see an opportunity to develop expertise that could be valuable as an academic in my country in the future. The program's global and clinical bioethics concentration offers me the perfect foundational grounding. However, I recognize that my writing skills need significant improvement to navigate this program successfully, especially to meet the standards of Euclid University. While this initially concerned me, I feel confident that with time and practice, I can develop the necessary writing skills to succeed in the course.

2) REFLECTIONS ON COURSE (ACA-401D)

Initially, I found the open-ended nature of the response paper (RP) assignment overwhelming. The lack of a structured template or specific guidelines for a topic to write on, with not even the word limit stated, was discouraging at first. However, upon revisiting the course material, particularly the first chapter on writing an academic essay, I realized this approach might be intentional. It seems to be designed to foster creativity and encourage a deeper analysis of the course material. This open-ended approach forces students to think critically about potential topics and organize information effectively. For example, in my case, despite the freedom to choose any topic related to the study material, I found it challenging to settle on one. My mind would hop from one topic to another, or I would struggle with writer's block. After some consideration, I decided to focus my RP1 on self-reflection on what I have learned from the first period of the course. Here, I summarize what I learned about the four important chapters in the study material, for a novice academic writer like me. In my own words, I summarize some main rules about the Turabian style- I did not know before. However, since these are rules, it proved difficult to paraphrase the sentences in my own words without using most of the words used in the source.

a) The Essence of Good Essay Writing

While I have written many essays, I have never truly reflected on what makes an essay engaging. The course material emphasized that writing requires "both creative and critical thinking" (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 9). The course provided helpful, practical tips for essay writing. I liked the idea of writing the "first draft" as early as possible, taking notes, and jotting down ideas about writing the response paper simultaneously when reading the study materials (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 10–11). The rule of thumb of writing clearly without being boring was hard for me. I often get writer's block because I worry my writing is dull. It bothers me when I repeat words in my essay. I keep waiting for more original ideas. Everything I write seems to come from others and, therefore, requires many citations. This makes it challenging to express my thoughts confidently. I intend to write more and freely express my thoughts to avoid writer's block. I will develop the habit of reading more academic papers to understand and improve my writing.

b) Punctuation

This course has significantly enhanced my understanding of punctuation. Previously, I was unaware of the types of brackets and their specific uses. Now, I am confident in applying them correctly in my writing. The course also clarified the subtle distinction between colons and semicolons, which had always been an area of confusion for me. The comprehensive eight-page section on punctuation was truly enlightening. While familiar with essential punctuation marks, I discovered I had been using some correctly while misplacing them at other times without fully understanding the rules. Surprisingly, I encountered punctuation marks that I had never used before, for example,

ellipsis, m-dash, and n-dash despite studying English throughout my life, including graduate school. This realization underscores the importance of continual learning and refinement of writing skills, even for those with good exposure to English-medium education.

c) American vs. British English

The most challenging aspect of the course was distinguishing between UK and US English. I realized that my English is a blend of both, making maintaining consistency in one style throughout a piece of writing particularly difficult. While the chapter on this topic is clear and understandable, the distinctions only stick in my memory for a short time. This is likely due to years of using English in a mixed form without adhering to specific guidelines. The ingrained habit of switching between UK and US conventions makes it hard to consistently apply one style, even when aware of the differences. This challenge highlights the complexity of language usage and the impact of our personal language histories on our writing practices. To learn this, I have started watching some videos on this topic on YouTube often to understand the expected differences, which would give me more recollection of memories that I can retain in my mind longer.

d) Style Guide and CMS

The section on the style guide and Chicago Manual of Style (CMS) was the most enlightening part of my studies in this period. While I have experience writing in styles like APA, AMA, and Vancouver, this was the first time I had encountered the Turabian style. I learned that when CMS is applied to theses and dissertations, it is called the Turabian style. Almost everything in this section was new to me, and I found several aspects beneficial for adopting the Turabian style. I list here the rules that are important for me to follow because I do not know these a priori or I err with these rules frequently in my writing:

1. I discovered that abbreviations are not used in the text and need to be spelled out, though they can be used in parenthetical comments. This was a notable difference from my usual writing, where I would use the abbreviation, for example, the use of abbreviation, i.e., in the text, without following any rules and restrictions (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 44).

2. The capitalization rules in the Turabian style were well spelled out. Capitalization is not allowed for articles (a, an, the), prepositions (against, between, in, of), conjunctions (and, but, nor, for, or, so, yet), or the infinitive "to" (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 45). Interestingly, we must capitalize the first word after a colon for heading and sentence capitalization. I must have erred many times in my earlier writing regarding this rule. When it comes to capitalizing regions, I am still trying to understand why we capitalize "Central America" but not "central Europe" or "central Asia". The course material needs to give a convincing explanation for this. I tried googling and could not find a satisfactory answer. It may be more appropriate to ask the course coordinator when I

submit this response paper. I learned that "Web" is always capitalized in terms like Web page, Web site, Web cam, and Web cast. The reason given for this is because "Web" is a proper noun in these terms, but I feel even terms like webmaster are so. For now, I would need to memorize the above four words where "Web" is capitalized (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 45–46).

3. The rules for compound words were particularly enlightening. Full-time compound words are meant to be hyphenated, and the dictionary is the best resource for finding out if a word is a compound word. Conditional compound words are hyphenated when used as adjectives but not as nouns. The example used in the study material with "role-playing" when used as an adjective and "role playing" when used as a noun in the same sentence clarified this concept. When using hyphens, I must have made plenty of mistakes in placing or not placing hyphens in the sentences. The course material taught me to hyphenate any prefixes before proper nouns, numbers, or capitalized abbreviations and that fractions are always hyphenated. An exciting rule I noted was about serial compounds with a common base, where the base is omitted in all but the last modifier, but hyphens are retained, like in "long- and short-term memory, 2-, 3-, and 10-min trials" (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 46).

4. Regarding numbers, precise measurements are always written in numerals, while round numbers are spelled out. Whole numbers from one through one hundred are always written out, and numbers from twenty-one to ninety-nine require a hyphen. When writing numbers with symbols, both need to be spelled out, except for percentages. I also noted that the standard American date format (month, date, year) is fine (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 47–48).

5. Brackets are used to indicate added words or emphasis in original quotes. Using "sic" in italics within brackets inside quotation marks can help quote the original work accurately. I can ignore citations to another quote if I am quoting material that contains a citation to another work. Block quotes in Turabian style are used for quotes longer than two or more sentences that run to 8 lines or more, which differs from other styles (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 49). However, this seems to conflict with the rules mentioned in the Chicago Manual of Style, which states in the chapter on drafting papers that "for five or more lines, set them off as an indented block" (Turabian 2007). The reference citations in quotes can be omitted in CMS, and if there are italics or bold fonts for emphasis in the original text, this should be mentioned in a note (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 49).

6. The Chicago page formatting guidelines, I found, are very particular. However, the font rules are similar to the ones I regularly use (i.e., Times New Roman twelve-point for text and ten-point for notes), while the right-ragged margin rule for manuscripts is new for me. All writing is to be double-spaced except block quotations, notes, captions, and long headings (which are single-spaced). Page numbering also has specific rules, with the page number at the bottom center (for major sections) and the rest at the upper right corner (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 50).

7. For footnotes, numerals are to be used on the line followed by a period and using shortened forms of references in subsequent citations instead of "ibid." and "idem." (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 52). I checked how the endnotes and references are cited and learned how to use Zotero from the video provided in the courses which makes it not very necessary to memorize the exact format.

3) CONCEPTS THAT ARE NOT CLEAR YET

I note below the concepts I still need clarification on after studying the study material. I have mentioned it here so that I can get it clarified by the course coordinator when he reviews this draft.

Q1. When we write more than two sentences expressing ideas borrowed from the same source, do we cite them individually after each sentence or only once after the completion of the whole sentence or paragraph? If we follow the latter, how do we differentiate whether the earlier sentences before the last cited sentence are the author's statements or if they have citations?

Q2. For a paraphrased paragraph with two different references, do we put the reference after the end of the whole paragraph or after every sentence?

Q3. Does an academic degree have a period when you write it? Ph.D. vs. PhD? This is clarified in the study material of the subsequent periods.

Q4. Why do we capitalize "Central America" but not "central Europe" or "central Asia"? I could not find a convincing reason.

4) CONCLUSION

Period one of the course was an eye-opening introduction to the Turabian and the Chicago Manual of Style in academic writing for me. I believe the coursepack provided is summarized and easy-to-read material from the book "A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations" by Kate L. Turabian. While I have learned a lot from this, the more consistent usage of these style rules in the subsequent period will make me champion the art of writing using this style.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2024. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 5th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.

Turabian, Kate L. 2007. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. 9th ed. Chicago and London: The University of Chicago Press.

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